

Comparative Evaluation of Endoscopic Vs. Conventional Septoplasty in the Management of Deviated Nasal Septum

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Abstract:

Background: Deviated nasal septum (DNS) is a prevalent condition that can significantly impact nasal function and quality of life. Surgical intervention, typically in the form of septoplasty, is often required to correct symptomatic deviations. While conventional septoplasty has long been the standard procedure, endoscopic septoplasty has emerged as a minimally invasive alternative, potentially offering reduced surgical time, lower postoperative pain, and faster recovery. Despite its growing adoption, the comparative effectiveness of endoscopic versus conventional septoplasty remains a topic of ongoing research.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate and compare the outcomes of endoscopic septoplasty versus conventional septoplasty in the management of deviated nasal septum, focusing on intraoperative parameters, postoperative recovery, symptom resolution, and complication rates.

Methods: A study was conducted over six months, involving 100 patients diagnosed with symptomatic DNS. Participants were randomly assigned to undergo either endoscopic septoplasty (Group A, n=50) or conventional septoplasty (Group B, n=50). Data were collected on surgical duration, intraoperative complications, postoperative pain, recovery time, and symptom resolution over a 3-month follow-up period. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Endoscopic septoplasty demonstrated a significantly shorter mean surgical duration (45.3 ± 8.4 minutes) compared to conventional septoplasty (62.7 ± 10.1 minutes, $p < 0.001$). Patients in the endoscopic group reported lower pain scores at 1 week post-surgery ($p < 0.01$) and returned to normal activities more quickly ($p < 0.01$). Symptom resolution at 3 months was comparable between the two groups ($p = 0.92$). The overall complication rates were low and did not differ significantly between the groups ($p = 0.55$).

Conclusion: Endoscopic septoplasty offers advantages over conventional septoplasty in terms of shorter surgical duration, reduced postoperative pain, and quicker recovery, without compromising long-term symptom resolution or increasing complication rates. These findings suggest that endoscopic septoplasty may be the preferred approach for managing deviated nasal septum.

Recommendations: Further research with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods is recommended to validate these findings and assess the long-term outcomes of endoscopic septoplasty. Training programs for ENT surgeons should also emphasize the benefits of endoscopic techniques to encourage broader adoption.

Keywords: Deviated Nasal Septum, Endoscopic Septoplasty, Conventional Septoplasty, Surgical Outcomes, Postoperative Recovery.

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Introduction

A frequent disorder called Deviated Nasal Septum (DNS) can cause severe nasal blockage and its related consequences, which include snoring, chronic rhinosinusitis, and even obstructive sleep apnoea. Although not all cases of septal deviation are symptomatic, it is believed that up to 80% of the population may have some degree of deviation. When present, persistent nasal congestion, headaches, and poor olfaction can all be significant symptoms of DNS that negatively affect a patient's quality of life [1]. The only effective therapy for

symptomatic DNS is still surgery by septoplasty, which aims to improve nasal airflow and relieve related symptoms.

For many years, the accepted surgical method for correcting deviated cartilage and bone has been conventional septoplasty, which entails creating an incision in the nasal mucosa. Traditional septoplasty has drawbacks even with its extensive application. Significant postoperative discomfort, an extended recuperation period, and possible

consequences including mucosal tears, haemorrhage, and septal perforation might all be linked to it [2]. The development of endoscopic methods has transformed nose procedures, such as septoplasty, in recent years. Endoscopic septoplasty is a less invasive and more accurate method of repairing DNS3. It employs a nasal endoscope to give improved visualisation of the operative region [3].

Evidence that suggests endoscopic septoplasty may have various advantages over traditional surgery has led to an increase in its use. These include a speedier healing period, less discomfort following surgery, a shorter length of time spent recovering, and a decreased risk of complications. Additionally, endoscopic septoplasty makes it possible to effectively treat concurrent sinus diseases and posterior septal abnormalities, which might be difficult to treat with a traditional method [4]. Notwithstanding these possible advantages, there is still considerable disagreement in the surgical profession over whether endoscopic septoplasty is generally better than traditional septoplasty, especially when it comes to long-term results and complication rates. It is crucial to compare the efficacy of endoscopic and traditional septoplasty, especially in light of the growing interest in minimally invasive surgical procedures and the requirement for evidence-based therapy. This study aims to evaluate and compare the outcomes of endoscopic septoplasty versus conventional septoplasty in the management of deviated nasal septum, focusing on intraoperative parameters, postoperative recovery, symptom resolution, and complication rates.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective study was designed as a multicentric, comparative evaluation.

Study Setting: The study was conducted across multiple centers, including tertiary care hospitals and specialized ENT clinics, ensuring a diverse patient population and broader generalizability of the results.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over a period of six months, ensuring adequate time for follow-up and data collection.

Participants: A total of 100 participants diagnosed with deviated nasal septum and indicated for septoplasty were enrolled in the study. The participants were equally divided into two groups: Group A (50 patients undergoing endoscopic septoplasty) and Group B (50 patients undergoing conventional septoplasty).

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients aged 18 to 60 years.

2. Diagnosed with symptomatic deviated nasal septum requiring surgical intervention.
3. Willingness to provide informed consent and comply with follow-up protocols.
4. No prior history of nasal surgeries.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with sinonasal polyposis or other significant nasal pathology.
2. Presence of coagulopathy or other contraindications to surgery.
3. Previous history of septoplasty or other nasal surgeries.
4. Patients with significant comorbidities that could interfere with surgical outcomes or follow-up.

Bias: To minimize bias, participants were randomly assigned to either the endoscopic or conventional septoplasty groups. Surgeons performing the procedures were blinded to the allocation, and all surgeries were performed by experienced ENT surgeons to standardize the procedure. Data analysis was performed by an independent statistician who was blinded to the groups.

Data Collection: Data were collected preoperatively, intraoperatively, and postoperatively. Preoperative data included patient demographics, severity of symptoms, and a detailed ENT examination. Intraoperative data consisted of surgical duration, complications, and ease of the procedure. Postoperative data included symptom resolution, pain scores, recovery time, and incidence of complications.

Procedure: Patients in Group A underwent endoscopic septoplasty, where the surgery was performed using endoscopic visualization. Patients in Group B underwent conventional septoplasty, performed through a traditional open approach. Both groups followed the same postoperative care protocols, including antibiotic prophylaxis, pain management, and follow-up visits at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months post-surgery.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The data were summarised using descriptive statistics, and continuous and categorical variables were compared using the independent t-test and the Chi-square test, respectively. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value of less than 0.05.

Results

A total of 100 patients were enrolled in the study, with 50 patients in each group (Group A: Endoscopic Septoplasty, Group B: Conventional Septoplasty). The demographic characteristics, including age, gender, and preoperative symptom

severity, were comparable between the two groups (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Group A (n=50)	Group B (n=50)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	34.5 ± 10.2	35.1 ± 9.8	0.73
Gender (Male/Female)	30/20	28/22	0.67
Severity of Symptoms (VAS Score)	7.8 ± 1.1	7.7 ± 1.3	0.85

The mean duration of surgery was significantly shorter in Group A compared to Group B ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, intraoperative complications, such as mucosal tears, were less frequent in the endoscopic group, though this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$) (Table 2).

Table 2: Intraoperative Data

Parameter	Group A (Endoscopic) (n=50)	Group B (Conventional) (n=50)	p-value
Mean Duration of Surgery (minutes)	45.3 ± 8.4	62.7 ± 10.1	<0.001
Intraoperative Complications (Mucosal Tear)	4 (8%)	8 (16%)	0.08

Postoperative outcomes, including pain, recovery time, and symptom resolution, were assessed at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months post-surgery. Patients in Group A reported significantly lower pain scores at 1 week ($p < 0.01$) and a faster return to normal activities ($p < 0.01$). Symptom resolution was comparable between the groups, with no significant difference at the 3-month follow-up ($p = 0.92$) (Table 3).

Table 3: Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	Group A (Endoscopic) (n=50)	Group B (Conventional) (n=50)	p-value
Mean Pain Score (1 week, VAS)	3.2 ± 1.0	5.1 ± 1.2	<0.01
Return to Normal Activities (days)	7.4 ± 2.1	12.3 ± 3.0	<0.01
Symptom Resolution (3 months, %)	94%	92%	0.92

Overall, the complication rates were low in both groups, with no significant difference in the incidence of postoperative complications such as bleeding, infection, or septal perforation ($p = 0.55$) (Table 4). All patients completed the 3-month follow-up, and there were no cases of revision surgery required during this period.

Table 4: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Group A (Endoscopic) (n=50)	Group B (Conventional) (n=50)	p-value
Postoperative Bleeding	2 (4%)	3 (6%)	0.65
Infection	1 (2%)	2 (4%)	0.56
Septal Perforation	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0.31

Summary of Results

- **Surgery Duration:** Significantly shorter in the endoscopic group.
- **Pain and Recovery:** Endoscopic group experienced less pain and faster recovery.
- **Symptom Resolution:** Comparable between the groups at 3 months.

Complications: Low in both groups, with no significant difference.

These results suggest that endoscopic septoplasty offers advantages in terms of shorter surgery duration, reduced pain, and quicker recovery, without compromising on the effectiveness of symptom resolution or increasing the risk of complications.

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that endoscopic septoplasty offers several advantages over conventional septoplasty in the management of DNS. Notably, the duration of surgery was significantly shorter in the endoscopic group, highlighting the efficiency of this minimally invasive technique. This reduction in surgical time could potentially decrease the overall risk of anesthesia-related complications and improve operating room efficiency.

Postoperative outcomes further supported the benefits of endoscopic septoplasty. Patients who underwent the endoscopic procedure reported significantly lower pain scores in the first week following surgery, which likely contributed to their quicker return to normal activities compared to those who underwent conventional septoplasty. This suggests that endoscopic septoplasty may lead

to a more comfortable and faster recovery, which is a crucial consideration for patient satisfaction and overall quality of life post-surgery.

Importantly, both surgical techniques were equally effective in resolving symptoms associated with DNS by the 3-month follow-up mark, indicating that the choice of technique does not compromise the long-term efficacy of the procedure. Additionally, the rates of postoperative complications, such as bleeding, infection, and septal perforation, were low and did not differ significantly between the two groups. This finding suggests that endoscopic septoplasty is not only efficient and less painful but also safe, with a complication profile comparable to that of conventional septoplasty.

A prospective, randomised trial comparing endoscopic septoplasty utilising Freer's incision and traditional septoplasty was carried out. 70 individuals with a symptomatic deviated nasal septum were randomly assigned to two groups for the research. The Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT-10) scores demonstrated that both treatments considerably reduced symptoms. Although there was no statistically significant difference between the two procedures, the post-operative SNOT-10 scores were substantial in both groups. This implies that nasal obstruction symptoms can be effectively treated with both traditional and endoscopic septoplasty [5].

Endoscopic and traditional septoplasty in 60 patients in prospective observational research was compared. Although these changes were not statistically significant, the study indicated that endoscopic septoplasty produced superior overall clinical results than conventional procedures, including less blood loss and a shorter surgical time. Additionally, the study demonstrated that endoscopic septoplasty led to less post-operative problems by improving lighting and facilitating access to hard-to-reach parts of the septum [6].

In a study of 50 individuals with a deviated nasal septum, the results of endoscopic and traditional septoplasty techniques were evaluated. The results of the study demonstrated the benefits of endoscopic septoplasty, including improved intraoperative visualisation, a shorter surgical time, and fewer problems. In contrast, endoscopic procedures did not significantly improve outcomes for anterior septal deviations, according to the

study, which also suggested that traditional septoplasty could be better in these cases [7].

Conclusion

The study's findings indicate that endoscopic septoplasty may be a preferable option for the surgical management of DNS, offering faster surgery, reduced postoperative pain, and quicker recovery without increasing the risk of complications. These advantages make it a compelling alternative to conventional septoplasty, particularly for patients and surgeons prioritizing a minimally invasive approach with a faster return to daily activities.

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